

THE DIRECT METHOD IN TEACHING COMMUNICATIVE SKILLS

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Annotation: This article is due to the fact that the issues of teaching communicative skills at school is studied insufficiently and require more attention and methodological development.

Keywords: direct method, communicative skills, role-plays, communication

The formative experiment's goal is to provide a series of training sessions with exercises meant to improve communication and voice coherence. General formation experiment tasks:

1. Enhancing communication abilities;
2. Encouraging younger students' initiative in the learning of a foreign language by helping them to produce meaningful speech;
3. Encouraging the growth of young pupils' creative capabilities;
4. When using an approach to the development of coherent speech, younger students' individual attitudes toward participation in the lessons are taken into consideration.

Desired learning objectives:

- 1) Students will learn the English language system and how to use language-based communication tools.
- 2) Students will learn how to communicate both orally and in writing, establish and maintain contact with a communication partner, request information of various volumes and types, speak logically and consistently, and appropriately respond to a communication partner's statements. They will

also learn how to use a variety of strategies to extract information from spoken or written text and interpret the information they have been given.

- 3) Through the lessons, students learn how to overcome feelings of alienation, self-doubt, a lack of communication, an inability to express their opinions, a fear of being misunderstood, ethnocentrism and ethno-egoism, aggression, indecision, and indifference to what is going on.

Throughout the lessons, games and exercises in communication were used.

The educational and methodological complex (EMC) is one of the important components that makes up the methodological instruments for the development of communication skills in a foreign language session.

Any teacher-experimenter will approach the learning process creatively based on his own traits and the abilities of his students, but he must exercise creativity within the EMC while adhering to all of its tenets.

There are unique pedagogical and methodological complexities in the English language in the present day. Each one includes a textbook as well as a book for the instructor, a workbook, audio cassettes for use at home and in the classroom, and handouts.

Reading and interpreting the sentences was done in turns by the pupils. Following that, the task was to ask each other the same question using established phrases. A game that was also meant to help people get to know one another came next.

Playing a role in “In two circles”: It is playable right away after the first instruction. Students practice the speech of acquaintance when they play this game for the first time. Children are split into two equal teams, each of which stands in a circle with an interior and exterior face. They do an introduction dialogue in pairs, after which the inner circle moves aside and the pairs switch, and the interaction is then repeated with more participants. Each student will speak the conversation five

times when there are ten kids in the class. The game is then played again using the fresh lexical content after a few lessons:

- Hello!
- Hi!
- What is your name?
- My name is Kate. What is your name?
- I am Peter. How old are you?
- I am 6. How old are you?
- I am 7. Goodbye!
- Bye!

2. The following lesson's theme was "Animals". In activity 13, the students learnt about various animals and how to categorize them based on color. The trainees are then exposed to a modal verb like "can" in exercise 14, at which point they are able to talk about what their pet is capable of doing. This can also be helped by the game we played with the kids.

The game, which I.A. Winter claims provides a psychological rationale for moving to a new language of instruction, serves as the foundation for teaching children oral communication in a foreign language in primary school. The use of a game to develop communication skills in elementary school enables the teacher to create speech tasks that specify the usage of the required communication patterns and have a reason and purpose for speech action (E.I. Negnevitskaya).

For instance, the following speech assignment may be made available to pupils in elementary school as part of a training program for the communication model "My (dog) is gray": "Our cherished pets were transformed into apples by an evil witch. It is important to reveal some information about them in order to disenchant them (which is a game motivation); this verbal act serves this objective. All students discuss their pets after the teacher, who provides an example of how to solve a communicative problem.

- The instructor: My cat is gray.
- A1: My dog is a large, brown dog.
- A2: My parrot is a yellow and green color.

The more game strategies the instructor employs, the more engaging the assignments and engaging the lectures are, the better the students are able to retain the information. A communicative game is an educational exercise that combines language, communication, and activity tasks, according to methodological definitions.

Playing "Be careful": Students must accurately respond to questions the teacher poses to them. The ball is suggested to be used for this activity. The teacher is positioned in the middle of a circle of students. He throws the ball while posing the subsequent queries. When challenged, the kids respond by kicking the ball back into the teacher's hands. As a result, the assignment is carried out with active participation from every kid in the class.

- Can a bird run?
 - Can a dog fly?
 - Can a fish jump?
 - Can a bird fly?
 - Can a lion dance?
 - Can a tiger sing?
 - Can a frog jump?
- And so on.

Playing "Guess who I am": Additionally, the improvement of monologue speech is a goal. Each student or couple, depending on the subject, choose an animal, career, month of the year, food or drink, etc., and explains and defines this object or idea without giving it a name. Other teams or students have to make educated guesses about what or who is being addressed.

For example: I can fly, I can sing (a bird). I am green and I can jump (a frog).

Playing «Describe a picture»: For instance, the instructor may summon one student to his desk and show him an image that the other students are not allowed

to see. The learner then describes what is seen in the image without mentioning the actual thing.

This method often focuses on honing and solidifying grammatical abilities. can be applied to both middle school and elementary school.

«**Ranking activities**»: The distribution of the information obtained in accordance with specific criteria is provided by the ranking activity job. For instance, students are given a list of adjectives that characterize a person. They must decide in groups whether three descriptors best describe a friend, lover, or instructor, and then rank those adjectives in order of significance. A presentation with reasoning and following discussion follow the rating of the data.

Additional techniques included:

1. Creating mini-dialogues to practice different grammatical constructions, such as:

- Do you speak English?
- Yes, I do.
- Do you have pets?
- No, I don't.
- Do you like apples?
- Yes, I do.
- Do you like playing football?
- No, I don't.

2. The "Conversation of the Rabbit and Winnie the Pooh" role-playing game is structured as follows:

The instructor assigns roles to the kids after dividing the class into groups and using cards with character descriptions. It lasts for three to five minutes.

These methods make it possible to fill a statement with a variety of linguistic tools in addition to strengthening and developing lexical grammatical abilities.

The communicative activities related to communicating in a foreign language are those that students are most interested in. If they are required to utilize words in conversation, they acquire words considerably more effectively.

The foundation for students' acquisition of new words, phrases, and expressions in English classes is conversational assignments designed to facilitate dialogue amongst students.

The research showed that English is the national language and people pay more attention to their level of speaking and having an appropriate communicative skill. During studying this work, we tried to find out the characteristic features of the present-day varieties of ways and methods of teaching communicative skills of the English language. We have done it by solving assigned tasks:

1. We gave the definition to the notion "communicative technique", investigated types of dialects and variants of the English language.
2. We determined the historical background and geography of varieties of the direct method through which we teach communicative skills.
3. We found out the principles of teaching communicative skills using the direct method.

It was revealed that a dialect is a variety of a language. Relational abilities are the capacity to send and get data. What's more, right away it appears to be that there isn't anything muddled in this. Eventually, as youngsters, we figured out how to talk and comprehend another person's discourse. However, the quintessence here isn't just in that frame of mind of data accordingly, yet additionally in the capacity to offer one's viewpoints as precisely as could be expected, to catch the importance of information disclosed by the conversationalist and sufficiently answer others' messages. This is successful correspondence.

We continually hear that great communicative abilities are crucial in both expert and individual life. They permit us to all the more effectively find a typical language with various individuals, work all the more successfully in a group and move up the profession stepping stool quicker. What precisely does the expression "open abilities" mean, for what reason would they say they are so significant for

progress? Also, at last, how would it be advisable for me I further develop them?- I attempted to respond to every one of the inquiries in this course work.

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